

THE PLACE OF DIGITAL SCULPTING IN ART

Usmanov Nodirbek Shavkatovich

Institute of Arts and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod

Head of the Department of Sculpture

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the role of digital sculpture in art, ease of learning digital sculpture programs, innovation process of computer technology; sculpture development based on 3 D software technology application and application of current digitization sculpture, modeling of complex objects, independent directions of digital sculpture in the field of three-dimensional computer graphics, auxiliary component in three-dimensional modeling.

Key words: digital sculpting, modeling, auxiliary component, computer graphics.

Introduction:

Digital sculpture is more and more common in our lives. At present, modern sculpture not only presents a trend of interdisciplinary development, but also increases its tolerance. Effectively embraces advances in digital sculpture, installation, architecture and conceptual art. In particular, it tries to incorporate visual art and other visual methods into the form of contemporary sculpture, which means time and process, meaning presentation. The origin of the art of creating voluminous forms from various materials undoubtedly dates back to ancient times, the period of the formation of human cultural development.

Literature analysis and methodology:

Human society steps into digitization age with the rapid development of information technology. Meanwhile, sculpture realm also occurs significant change. More and more works created based on digital technology appear. That is, digitization sculpture (or termed as sculpture based on 3D software). Digitization sculpture is the cross of art and computer science and the subject integrating sensibility and reason.

Digital art at home and abroad are all in starting stage because of its youth. Compared to traditional sculpture technique, sculpture based on 3D software occurs significant changes on material and art form presentation. Sculpture creation based on 3D software plays important function on statuary realm especially environment sculpture because computer sculpture creation is characterized by virtuality, interaction and high efficiency. Freedom and high efficiency of creation technique and diversity of creation platform change sculpture creation and promote the communication between public and art.

Digital sculpture gradually ceases to be a unique phenomenon and is increasingly used in various areas of human life. Of course, this became possible due to the rapid development of technology, the growth of computer technology indicators and its access to a wide range of users. If previously an ordinary sculptor working with clay, stone or synthetic materials with his hands, scalpel or rasp was engaged in sculpting for both artistic and technical purposes, then a 3D artist (Digital Sculptor) processes a 3D model.

Mainly, digital sculpting is used to render high-poly, organic 3D models of bright surfaces with very large and small details. Digital sculpture gradually ceases to be an unusual phenomenon

and is increasingly used in various areas of human life, attracting not only lovers of unusual, fantastic creatures and practicing designers, but also researchers.

Results:

Digitization sculpture is created on computer platform based on some software. Advance with time of art is inevitable development process. Sculpture developed from traditional sculpture creation to current digitization sculpture. Innovation of computer technology promotes revolution of creation technique and presentation form of sculpture in different degrees and presents freedom and high efficiency of digitization sculpture technique, diversification of creation platform and naturalization and emotion of interactive process.

Computer brings unprecedented revolution for sculpture. Digitization sculpture breaks traditional observation and visual pattern. This paper discussed the conflict, effect and challenge of digitization sculpture and analyzed trend and digitization development in the future based on the revolution research on computer technology innovation and digitization sculpture and status analysis of current digitization sculpture application.

Discussion:

Indeed, the modeling of complex objects allows the creation of various biological entities, opening up new possibilities for cinema, animation, computer games and advertising. Meanwhile, digital sculpture has found its way into other fields as well. Digital sculpting is increasingly used in various fields of human life, gradually ceasing to be an exception in three-dimensional modeling, and becoming a tool not only for professional three-dimensional modelers, computer graphics enthusiasts, but also for teachers of additional education. is also attracting attention. In today's world, digital sculpting and the entertainment industry go hand in hand, and this alliance is at the forefront of digital sculpting applications. Indeed, the modeling of complex objects allows the creation of various biological entities, opens up new possibilities for cinema, animation and computer games.

Digitization sculpture gradually changes new demand and standard of public for aesthetic. Art appreciation pattern transforms. The boundary between art and technology becomes vague. But the combination of art maturity and technology involution becomes closer. Popularization and diversification close the communication between people and art.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that the ease of learning digital sculpting programs makes it possible to include 3D modeling in the educational activities of the Institute from the first stage. Not "adult", but interesting 3D objects created by students increase the motivation to go deeper into the world of 3D computer graphics, to develop interest in other types of 3D modeling. In the process of 3D sculpting, students demonstrate competence in the fields of: mathematics, geometry, biology and anatomy, visual arts, computer science; gain practical experience in analyzing the shape of an object, developing elements and creating a 3D model; Gain professional experience as a 3D modeler and designer. Digital sculpture is becoming a means for students to achieve personal and meta-subject learning outcomes.

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